

INTRODUCTION

Meat products are an essential part of the Russian agro-industrial complex and a significant source of income for agriculture. Studying Russia's role in the global meat market allows us to understand how it can improve its position and increase exports. Russia's role as a meat producer may be the key to ensuring food stability domestically and internationally.

In recent years, Russia has faced economic sanctions leading to the need to develop its production and look for new markets. This creates an interest in researching the current state and prospects of the meat industry.

Russia is facing competition from other meat-producing countries. Studying competitive advantages and disadvantages can help develop strategies to increase competitiveness.

Thus, studying the role of the Russian Federation in the global market for meat and meat products is important for understanding the country's domestic and foreign policies and for developing effective strategies in the agricultural sector.

The article analyzes Russia's role in the global market for meat and meat products.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research materials were data from periodicals on the trends in the development of the meat industry, livestock and poultry farming in Russia, as well as statistical reports from the Russian Federation, its subjects, and the Ministry of Agriculture of Russia over the past decades. Abstract-logical, monographic, computational-constructive, comparative analysis (comparing Russia with other meat-producing countries to identify competitive advantages and disadvantages), and statistical methods were used in the research process.

SWOT analysis assessing strengths and weaknesses, opportunities, and threats for the meat industry in Russia was also used.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In 2021, the global food market faced intense pressure caused by the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on production and supply of food and agricultural products.

E. A. Nifontova and E. V. Khudyakova note the importance of analyzing the impact of market economy instability on the efficiency of the agro-industrial sector [1].

According to A. Arskiy and M. Khudzhatov, the EAEU's dependence on imports of specific categories of meat products exceeds 40%, and milk and dairy products – 26%. Due to disruptions in production chains caused by the pandemic, dependence on foreign suppliers may increase significantly [2].

S. K. Wegren and F. Nilssen conclude that Russia will remain an importer of food, although the structure of imported goods and trading partners will continue to change. The authors express cautious optimism that Russia will continue to be a major exporter of food [3].

S. K. Wegren believes that significant government interventions in the agricultural sector support the Russian export model. The author quotes that in May 2018, President Putin set the task for the agricultural sector to increase the value of food exports to \$45 billion by 2024, compared with \$26 billion in 2018 [4].

D. N. Osyanin et al. analyze the current state of the Russian meat industry and its export potential. The authors describe the problems in the system of state support and identify the main directions for its improvement [5].

A. R. Nabiyeu et al. provide a comprehensive assessment of the food security system and the place of the Russian agro-industrial complex in it. The authors formulate recommendations to increase the production of agri-food products through innovations, to increase productivity of fields and farms, save material resources, energy, and labor costs, increase labor productivity, and strengthen food security in Russia [6].

According to E. P. Afanaseva et al., the Russian Federation ranks 19th among the world's food exporters. Russia exports grain, fat and oil products, fish, and seafood. The authors concluded that while maintaining the current pace of development of the agro-industrial complex and considering the global food shortage, Russia can strengthen and expand its position in the worldwide food market [7].

E. A. Demakova and A. V. Semenov note a significant increase in Russian pork exports from 2018 to 2020. Export growth was achieved during the implementation of the industry's policy of import substitution and export orientation. According to the authors, further development of pork exports requires linking export opportunities with support measures and reducing barriers to Russian exports [8].

I. G. Ushachev et al. provide a long-term forecast of agricultural development based on a linear optimization model. The proposed model (partial equilibrium) optimizes distribution of material and cost resources in agriculture according to the criterion of maximizing food consumption by the Russian population [9].

I. F. Gorlov et al. give an overview of the livestock market, its trends and volumes after the EU and the United States introduced restrictive sanctions against Russia. The authors note that cattle production in Russia decreased compared to other segments [10].

A. A. Medvedev and T. G. Nefedova consider the main trends in the spatial organization of animal husbandry based on a large-scale study of the regions of the Central Federal District of Russia. According to the authors, the number of cattle in most areas continues to decline against the background of a general increase in meat production in recent years, mainly due to pork and poultry [11].

V. V. Maslova et al. emphasize that government support for construction of new high-tech pig breeding complexes allowed reconstructing and modernizing existing farms and establishing a new production base for Russian pig breeding. According to the authors, the country has reached full self-sufficiency in pork, but import dependence on pig embryos, veterinary vaccines, and premixes remains [12].

V. I. Chinarov et al. write that the Russian market of breeding products displays a positive trend towards an increase in breeding cattle sales. With high annual import substitution rates for breeding cattle, its sales increased by 62.3% in six years, which reduced imports to 15.6% [13]. The authors also proposed conceptual solutions to improve the competitiveness of milk, beef, and breeding production, ensuring the industry's recovery from stagnation. A set of new mechanisms of state regulation effectively impact the competitiveness of domestic producers of livestock products [14; 15].

Meat production in Russia is concentrated in several key regions. For example, the Central Federal District (including Moscow Oblast) and the Southern Federal District (including Krasnodar Krai) are the leaders in pork and beef production.

J. Zhou notes that China is a significant investment partner for developing agriculture in the Russian Far East [16].

V. Tsyngyeva et al. explore prospects for sheep industry development in the border regions of China, Mongolia, and the Trans-Baikal Territory of the Far Eastern Federal District of Russia. The authors propose directions for sheep industry development in the Trans-Baikal Territory to increase the industry's export potential and expand the quantity of sheep products in the markets of Mongolia and China [17].

V. V. Vorobyova et al. analyze the financial condition of agricultural enterprises in Altai Krai that carried out active investment activities but were liquidated due to financial insolvency. According to the authors, liquidation of large, financially insolvent enterprises significantly improved the structure of enterprises solvency in the region [18].

M. B. Ulimbashev and R. A. Ulimbasheva evaluate the productivity and quality of meat in Karachay sheep raised with various maintenance technologies and high-altitude belt systems in the mountainous regions of the North Caucasus [19].

Thus, this research topic covers various fields of knowledge, including economics, agronomy, veterinary medicine, ecology, and sociology. This allows us to look at the problem from different angles and better understand the factors affecting the meat market.

The study requires collecting and analyzing statistical data on meat production, consumption, export, and import in Russia and other countries. This includes using economic models and methods to assess market dynamics and trends.

Analyzing the impact of external factors such as international trade agreements, sanctions, changes in consumer preferences, and environmental regulations is necessary. This requires applying methods of political economy and international relations.

Current development of models for forecasting future trends in the meat market can be useful for decision-making at the state and business levels.

RESULTS

Three hundred forty-two million three hundred ninety-six thousand twenty tons of meat (42.8 kg per capita) are produced worldwide annually (see Table 1) [20].

The People's Republic of China is the world's largest meat producer, producing 88,156,383 tons per year.

The United States of America ranks second in production at 46,832,946 tons.

Brazil is the third-largest meat producer with 29,341,250 tons of production per year.

The Russian Federation, with 10,629,378 tons of production per year, is estimated at 4.

Table 1

Global meat production by country for 2020

Top 10 countries by total meat production			Top 10 countries by meat production per capita		
Country	Total, million tons	Per capita, kg	Country	Total, million tons	Per capita, kg
Republic of China	88.2	63.246	Denmark	1.9	323.743
United States of America	46.8	142.886	New Zealand	1.5	296.39
Brazil	29.3	140.032	Ireland	1.1	234.683
Russian Federation	10.6	72.369	Montserrat	0.001	191.429
Germany	8.2	98.971	Uruguay	0.66	188.854
India	7.5	5.578	Australia	4.7	185.974
Mexico	7.1	56.529	Netherlands	2.9	170.214
Spain	7.03	150.624	Belgium	1.8	159.891
Argentina	5.9	133.276	Spain	7.03	150.624
France	5.6	83.536	United States of America	46.8	142.886

Notably, the listed countries are leaders in terms of total meat production but significantly inferior to other countries in terms of product production per capita. Thus, in the world ranking of meat production per capita, China ranks 41st (63,246 kg), the USA 10th (142,886 kg), Brazil 11th (140,032 kg), and Russia 31st (72,369 kg).

Meat industry is one of the socially significant branches of the agro-industrial complex of the Russian Federation. The need for its development is due to the growing consumer demand for meat and meat products, an average degree of investment activity, and relatively high rates of dependence on imports. The industry accounts for 1.2% of Russia's GDP, and about 15% of the gross production of the food and food processing industry. Meat industry specifics are closely interrelated with one of the most essential branches of agriculture – animal husbandry. Therefore, ensuring economic growth and increasing the competitiveness of Russian producers in the meat and meat products market is possible only under the accelerated development of animal husbandry [21; 22].

By the end of 2021, total meat production remained at the same level (an increase of 5.9% was noted only in some regions, for example, in the Southern Federal District).

According to the information and analytical agency Emeat, in 2021, the production volume of the main types of meat (pork, beef, poultry, lamb, and goat meat) in all categories of farms in Russia amounted to 10.8 million tons in slaughter weight. This is 0.3%, or 33.7 thousand tons, more than in 2020 [23].

Thus, in 2021, poultry accounted for 45.7% of total meat production, pork accounted for 37.3%, beef accounted for 15.1%, and lamb and goat meat accounted for only 1.9% (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 Meat production by main species in Russia in 2021 (10.8 million tons)

In general, the country provides itself with this type of product by 89%. However, such indicators are valid only for pork and poultry meat, which Russia has been able to provide

itself with at the minimum required level. However, the domestic cattle industry is still lagging behind the targets in terms of beef production – the country produces only about 75% of what is needed [24]. This is due to the following issues:

1) relatively low production profitability. While pork and poultry provide 20% and 17% of the profit, respectively, beef provides only about 7-10%. With such profitability indicators, investors are much more willing to invest in pig and poultry farming than in cattle breeding for meat;

2) situation on the breeding stock market. According to experts, domestic breeding plants cannot meet domestic product demand today;

3) macroeconomic difficulties. The inflation and devaluation recorded in Russia in the last two years increased the cost of building materials and equipment needed for livestock complexes.

Production indicators vary significantly by federal district. In 2021, the regions of the Central Federal District accounted for 38.8% of production of the main types of meat in physical terms, this is about 4217 thousand tons in slaughter weight. Production growth in this district amounted to 33.8 thousand tons (+0.8%). In the Southern Federal District, meat production increased by 5.9%, or 54.5 thousand tons. In the Far East, production also increased by 8.6% (+16.4 thousand tons).

On the contrary, production figures in the Volga Federal District decreased by 0.2% (-3.6 thousand tons). The regions of the North-Western Federal District also showed negative dynamics, by 3.1% (-24.8 thousand tons).

In the North Caucasus region, meat production decreased by 0.7% (-5.0 thousand tons) and 0.8% (-7.8%) in the Siberian Federal District. However, the most significant decrease in production indicators is noted in the Ural Federal District, by 4.1% (-29.8 thousand tons) (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2 Meat production in the federal districts of Russia in 2021 (10808 thousand tons)

The past year was not the most favorable regarding the epizootic situation. Thus, according to the Rosselkhoznadzor data on hazardous and economically/socially significant diseases, in 2021, were recorded [25]:

- 268 outbreaks of African swine fever in Amur, Arkhangelsk, Belgorod, Bryansk, Vladimir, Volgograd, Voronezh, Ivanovo, Kaluga, Kostroma, Kursk, Magadan, Nizhny Novgorod, Novgorod, Orel, Pskov, Penza, Rostov, Samara, Saratov, Smolensk, Sverdlovsk, Tver, Tula, Tambov, Tver, Chelyabinsk and Yaroslavl Oblasts, as well as the Trans-Baikal, Primorsky, Perm, Stavropol and Khabarovsk Krai, in the Republics of Komi, Chuvashia, Mari El and Tatarstan, in Jewish Autonomous Oblast and Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Okrug;
- 68 outbreaks of avian influenza in Astrakhan, Belgorod, Kaliningrad, Kursk, Kurgan, Orenburg, Rostov, Samara, Saratov, Sverdlovsk, Tyumen, Chelyabinsk Oblasts, Krasnodar and Stavropol Krai, the Republics of Dagestan, Bashkortostan, Kalmykia, Tatarstan, Tyva, and the Udmurt Republic;
- 13 outbreaks of sheep and goat smallpox in the Ivanovo, Kostroma, Leningrad, and Yaroslavl Oblasts;
- 4 outbreaks of Newcastle disease in Nizhny Novgorod, Vladimir Oblast, Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Okrug, Primorsky Krai;
- 52 outbreaks of infectious nodular dermatitis in the Trans-Baikal Territory, the Republic of Bashkortostan, and Chelyabinsk Oblast;
- 1 outbreak of foot-and-mouth disease in Orenburg Oblast.

Another significant indicator is the comparative dynamics of the cost of certain types of meat. From 2013 to 2021, the price of 1 kg of pork exceeded that of 1 kg of broiler chicken meat. In the third quarter of 2021, prices for these categories were fixed at almost the same level. Based on the price dynamics over the past 9 years, notable growth peaks were noted in March 2014, summer 2018, and early 2021. The price movement for broiler chicken meat has smoother rises and decreases, often depending on seasonality, feed cost, and availability of hatching eggs. A different picture is observed about pork: prices for this meat category are highly variable and depend on many factors; therefore, its cost can change literally in one day [26].

At the end of December 2021, the cost of pork in half-carcasses of domestic production in the wholesale link was around 186.7 RUB/kg, which is 11.4% higher year-on-year. However, the average price for 2021 increased by 23.8% to 186.6 RUB/kg (relative to the average prices in 2020).

The cost of a broiler chicken carcass for the year (end of December 2021 – end of December 2020) increased by 33.4% and was around 141.6 RUB/kg by December 27, 2021. At the same time, the average price for a broiler chicken carcass in 2021 was 143.7 RUB/kg, which is 38.9% higher than the average values in 2020 [Stat].

CONCLUSION

Providing the population with products of our production is a matter of food and economic security for the country. Meat products are an indispensable source of animal protein. Accordingly, the consumption of meat products at the level of physiological standards is necessary to ensure the health of the nation. According to statistics, in 2021, the Russian population was provided with all types of meat and meat products at 74 kg per capita. Thus, at present, the production of meat and meat products has almost reached the indicator of the rational consumption rate, which is determined by the Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution "FRC Nutrition and Biotechnology" at the level of 70-75 kg per capita. At the same time, the physiological rate of consumption of meat and meat products (in terms of meat) is 82-86 kg per capita. To ensure the consumption of meat and meat products at the level of the physiological norm per capita, it is necessary to radically restructure the entire raw material base, supply chain, slaughter of livestock, and primary processing of meat raw materials, and develop an optimal structure for the production of meat and meat products.

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